

Study of Anticipated Transient Without Scram with the Coupled code TRACE-SubChanFlow for the SMART Small Modular Reactor

J. G. Etcheto¹, V. H. Sanchez-Espinoza¹, K. Zhang¹

¹Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany

javier.etcheto@kit.edu, victor.sanchez@kit.edu, Kanglong.zhang@kit.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an analysis of the behavior of the SMART Small Modular Reactor (SMR) during an Anticipated Transient Without SCRAM (ATWS). Two different approaches are used in the study: one using a traditional TRACE model for the entire SMART primary system, and the other utilizing a coupled code TRACE-SubChanFlow (SCF). Neutronic Point Kinetics (NPK) is used to model the core neutronic dynamic, and the secondary side is modeled with temperature boundary conditions defined in the Steam Generators (SGs) pipe walls. The study compares steady and transient states to evaluate the performance of the two approaches. The analysis provides valuable insights into the response of the SMART SMR in the event of an ATWS scenario, and may have implications for the safety and design of similar reactors.

KEYWORDS: SMART, TRACE, SUBCHANFLOW, ATWS

1. INTRODUCTION

In the McSAFER project, one of the main objectives is to evaluate the 3D Thermal-Hydraulic (TH) conditions within the integrated Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) of SMR designs, using TH standalone/coupled codes with different levels of detail (system level, subchannel level, and CFD level) [1]. Due to the integrated design, numerous components, including the helical steam generators, pumps, and pressurizer, are situated inside the RPV, resulting in a geometrically complex primary coolant path. As a result, a high level of flow mixing will occur, which cannot be accurately modeled using 1D TH models, whether under nominal or accidental conditions.

The following sections of this study will provide a detailed examination of the SMART design characteristics, followed by an in-depth presentation of the models and analysis results for the two computational approaches utilized. The conclusion and outlook of this research endeavor will be presented as the final part of this study.

1.1. SMART Reactor

The System-integrated Modular Advanced Reactor (SMART) is an SMR design developed by the Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI) [2][3][4] (Figure 1). The reactor is a PWR-type SMR that produces 330 MW of thermal power to generate 100 MW of electricity. The primary coolant circuit is integrated, i.e. all primary loop components are contained inside the RPV. The power is extracted from the RPV by eight modular-type, once-through helical steam generators, which produce 30 K superheated steam in the secondary side under nominal operating conditions. Four canned pumps circulate the forced-convection coolant flow through the RPV. The in-vessel pressurizer is designed to control the system

pressure at a nearly constant level over the entire design basis events [5]. The core is composed of 57 PWR-like fuel assemblies (FAs). A flow-mixing header assembly is located at the steam-generator outlet to create a uniform coolant mass flow at the core inlet. The reactor operates at about 15 MPa and the core inlet and outlet temperatures are 568.85 K and 596.15 K respectively [6].

Figure 1: SMART reactor pressure vessel and integrated primary loop [5][7].

1.2. Anticipated Transient Without Scram (ATWS)

In this study, the focus is on the analysis of an Anticipated Transient Without SCRAM (ATWS) accident. The accident is initiated by a complete loss of feed water resulting from the abrupt closure of all feed water isolation valves, while assuming that the automatic reactor SCRAM is disabled during the transient analysis. The power excursion of the reactor is controlled by the negative reactivity coefficients, and the feedback effects are computed by a point kinetic model of the core. The analysis assumes that the offsite power remains available, and therefore, the forced recirculation of coolant inside the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) is sustained [5][8].

The temperatures in the pipes of the Steam Generators (SGs) are considered as boundary conditions that vary with time. The primary side, i.e., RPV, is the main focus of the analysis, and the secondary side is not modeled.

Study of SMART ATWS with TRACE-SUBCHANFLOW

1.3. TRACE

The TRAC/RELAP Advanced Computational Engine (TRACE) code is a tool developed by the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission for analyzing the behavior of light water reactors during both steady-state and transient scenarios. It consolidates the capabilities of several legacy codes into a single computational tool, enabling best-estimate analyses of loss-of-coolant accidents, operational transients, and other accident scenarios [11].

The code can also model thermal-hydraulic phenomena in both one-dimensional (1D) and three-dimensional (3D) space, and includes models for multidimensional two-phase flow, non-equilibrium thermodynamics, generalized heat transfer, reflood, level tracking, and reactor kinetics.

Finite volume numerical methods are used to solve the partial differential equations that describe the two-phase flow and heat transfer, with a semi-implicit time-differencing technique used for evaluating heat transfer equations.

The code is based on a component approach to model reactor systems, with each physical piece of equipment represented as a component that can be further nodalized into physical volumes where fluid, conduction, and kinetics equations are evaluated.

TRACE's modeling approach for two-phase flow includes a full two-fluid hydrodynamic model, stratified-flow regime, mass balance, and dissolved solute tracking, with flow-regime dependent correlations used for interfacial heat, momentum, and energy transfer processes. However, the code does not evaluate the stress/strain effect of temperature gradient in structures or the effect of fuel-rod-gap closure due to thermal expansion or material swelling.

The code's execution time depends on the total number of mesh cells, the maximum allowable timestep size, and the rate of change of the phenomena being evaluated. The stability-enhancing two-step (SETS) numerics in hydraulic components allow for the use of very large time steps in slow transients, resulting in significant speedups in simulations of slow-developing accidents and operational transients.

TRACE utilizes either the Dittus-Boelter correlation or the Sieder-Tate correlation to estimate the Nusselt number, which is employed to ascertain the heat transfer coefficient in the coolant during forced convection heat transfer [12].

1.4. SubChanFlow

SubChanFlow is a code designed to simulate subchannel flow and heat transfer in rod bundles of light water reactors, such as pressurized water reactors (PWRs). It uses a subchannel analysis approach that divides the reactor core into subchannels and solves conservation equations for mass, momentum, and energy in each subchannel to determine the flow and temperature distribution in the reactor core.

SubChanFlow has been extensively validated against experimental data from various reactor types to ensure that its predictions of subchannel flow and heat transfer in light water reactors are accurate. In particular, SubChanFlow has been validated against the NUPEC PWR Tests (PSBT), and the results of the validation demonstrated good agreement between the code's predictions and experimental data. The successful validation indicates that SubChanFlow has the potential to be a valuable tool for safety and performance analyses of nuclear reactors [13].

SubChanFlow uses empirical heat transfer correlations for the prediction of the heat transfer coefficients in the fuel rods. The correlations used in SubChanFlow are based on the Chilton-Colburn analogy, which is a widely accepted approach to calculate convective heat transfer coefficients for turbulent flows. For turbulent flow in rod bundles, SubChanFlow uses the Dittus-Boelter correlation to calculate the convective heat transfer coefficient.

The heat field inside the fuel is calculated by solving the energy conservation equation, which takes into account the heat generated by nuclear fission in the fuel rods and the heat transferred to the coolant. The code divides the fuel rods into axial and radial nodes to capture the temperature gradients inside the fuel using the finite difference method.

1.5. Coupling methodology for TRACE and SCF

This study focuses on the use of the TRACE-SCF coupled code with a domain decomposition approach based on the ICoCo interface. In this approach, the SCF solver is used to model the core, while the rest of the primary system is modeled with the TRACE code. The MEDCoupling library is used to handle the inter-code data exchange automatically, with the exchange taking place at the core inlet and outlet planes. The meshes involved in the exchange are 2D, as shown in Figure 2. The exchange is carried out in both steady and transient states, and in the second one can be done explicitly or implicitly.

Figure 2: ICoCo TRACE-SCF Coupled code: SMART model.

2. DEVELOPED MODELS

2.1. TRACE Model

Figure 3 presents the TRACE Model for SMART, where the RPV is represented by the 3D vessel component with cylindrical discretization. This type of discretization allows for the representation of internal components, including the Flow Mixing Header Assemblies (FMHA) and the Flow Skirt.

The SMART Reactor consists of 8 Steam Generators located equidistantly inside the RPV, and therefore, the RPV is divided into 8 azimuthal cells. To model the complex geometry of the FMHAs, 3 radial cells are considered in the downcomer zone. Two additional radial cells are included to reproduce the radial space where the barrel and the core are located. Axially, the RPV is divided into 21 cells.

Study of SMART ATWS with TRACE-SUBCHANFLOW

The pressurizer is located in the upper part of the RPV and is modeled as a pressurizer-type pipe connected to the RPV with 8 pipes, which are also connected to safety relief valves. The opening and closing pressures of the safety relief valves are 18.7 MPa and 15.0 MPa, respectively. The Reactor Containment is modeled as a break component with a pressure of 0.1 MPa.

There are 4 centrifugal canned pumps located in the upper part of the RPV, each with a radial inlet suction and an axial discharge upstream to the steam generators. The primary side of the steam generators is modeled with pipes of the tube bank cross-flow type, which are connected to the RPV and to heat structures allowing heat exchange with the secondary circuit. During the ATWS scenario, the pump impellers' angular velocity remains constant.

The TRACE model includes FILLS and BREAKs, which are used as boundary conditions to cut out the TRACE model in the core region and exchange variables, such as mass flow rate, temperature, and pressure, with the SCF model. These components are indicated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The TRACE model for the SMART reactor.

2.2. SCF Model

The reactor core consists of 57 fuel assemblies, with each assembly being modeled as a channel that accounts for cross-flow using a mixing coefficient. The channels are divided into 20 cells along the axial direction. The representative fuel rod within each assembly is divided radially into 10 zones, and the heat transfer coefficient is determined using the Dittus Boelter correlation. To model neutronics, a Neutron Point Kinetic (NPK) model is used, incorporating reactivity coefficients predicted by PARCS [9].

3. RESULTS

This chapter will begin by presenting and discussing the results obtained from the use of TRACE-SA and TRACE-SCF, followed by a discussion of selected results for the transient phase.

3.1 Steady state simulation results

Table 1 compares the main TH plant parameters obtained from TRACE-SA and TRACE-SCF simulations with published literature data. The results show that the discrepancies between TRACE-SA and TRACE-SCF are small, with differences of less than 1% for all parameters except for the total mass flow rate. The mass flow rate in both simulations is nearly identical, but it is 11% higher than the literature value. The MCP rated mass flow rate will be used to correct this parameter in future simulations. It is important to note that the mass flow rate used produces a slightly lower core delta_T compared to the literature value.

Table 1: Steady state results.

Parameter	Literature [10]	TRACE-SA (diff %)*	TRACE-SCF (diff %)*
Primary pressure (MPa)	15.0	14.92 (0.5)	14.88 (0.8)
Core Power (MW)	330.0	330.0 (0.0)	330.0 (0.0)
Core inlet T (K)	568.85	568.56 (0.05)	568.28 (0.1)
Core outlet T (K)	596.15	594.07 (0.4)	592.37 (0.7)
Core delta_T (K)	27.30	25.53 (6)	24.09 (12)
Total mass flow rate (kg/s)	2090	2335 (11)	2337 (11)
Core pressure drop (kPa)	Between 5-45	25.7	26.3

$$* (\text{diff } \%) = \frac{|\text{Literature Value} - \text{Calculated Value}|}{\text{Literature Value}} * 100$$

3.2 Transient simulation results

For the ATWS accident, a simulation time of 500 s is considered. The first 100 s correspond to a steady state. At that time, the initiating event is produced.

Figure 4 gives the pressure evolution in the primary side (pressurizer) in both cases, TRACE -SA, and TRACE-SCF. The prediction in both has the same behavior.

During the first 100 s of the simulation, there are no pressure changes. When the loss of feed water is produced (ATWS initiating event), the steam generators are isolated. This produces a drop in the heat exchange between the primary and secondary sides, and consequently an increase in the primary side temperature and pressure.

When the Passive Residual Heat Removal System (PRHRS) is connected to the SGs (approximately 5 s after the beginning of the accident, according to previous simulations), the heat removal increases, and so the primary temperature and pressure go down. Here this phenomenon is represented by a temperature boundary condition in the SGs.

Figure 4 illustrates the primary pressure in both models. It is easier to maintain pressure stability in the TRACE-SA case because of the pressurizer's pressure control, whereas in the TRACE-SCF case, there is a slight drift in pressure during the first 100 seconds of the simulation. Nonetheless, pressure control is

Study of SMART ATWS with TRACE-SUBCHANFLOW

effective in both cases, and the drift is compensated for by the pressurizer heaters if the system is allowed to evolve further.

Figure 5 depicts the total power curves, which show that the results in both cases are quite similar for the first 150 seconds of the simulation. Although there are some differences after that time, which are caused by the variations in the total reactivity inserted in both cases (as seen in Figure 11), they both follow the same trend. It is important to note that the decrease in power is due to the negative TH reactivity coefficients. The power results have a similar trend to those obtained in a previous study (reference [7]).

Figure 4: Evolution of the primary pressure.

Figure 5: Evolution of the total power.

Figure 6 presents the total mass flow rate predicted by TRACE-SA and TRACE-SCF simulations. At 100 s, an increment is observed due to a change in the coolant properties caused by the temperature change. The MCPs are constantly running at a fixed impeller angular velocity throughout the simulation. The TRACE-SCF simulation predicts a slightly larger mass flow rate increment compared to TRACE-SA, but the difference decreases after 200 s. Despite the slight difference, the general behavior of the mass flow rate predicted by both models is highly similar.

Figure 6: Total mass flow rate.

Figure 7: Steam Generators average inlet temperatures.

In Figures 7 and 8, the SGs' average inlet and outlet temperatures are shown, respectively. The predictions of both models are similar for both variables, but there is an offset present in the inlet temperature, which is also observed in the steady-state part of the simulation. The TRACE-SA case predicts an inlet temperature that is 1.8 K higher than the TRACE-SCF case.

Figures 9 and 10 show the core fuel and coolant average temperatures during the transient, respectively. The core fuel average temperature predicted by TRACE-SA is higher than that predicted by TRACE-SCF, especially in the steady-state. Nevertheless, the behavior of both models is similar. In the case of the core coolant average temperature, the difference between both models is around 2 K, and their behavior is similar as well.

Figure 8: Steam Generators average outlet temperatures.

Figure 9: Core fuel average temperature.

Figure 11 illustrates the total, fuel, and moderator reactivities during the transient. As predicted from the core coolant average temperature (Figure 10), both models show similar moderator reactivity.

However, there is a significant difference in the fuel reactivity predicted by the two models, which increases from 100 s to 300 s of simulation and then remains practically constant. This difference can be attributed to the core fuel average temperature prediction. Figure 9 provides an explanation for this difference.

At the start of the transient, when the reference temperatures for the neutron kinetic models are applied, the temperature difference between the models is the greatest. The larger the change in this temperature difference, the greater the difference in the reactivity predicted by the models.

As the core fuel average temperature between the two models begins to decrease, the change in the temperature difference (relative to the initial condition) becomes more significant, leading to a greater difference in the reactivity.

The predicted total reactivity is the sum of the fuel and moderator reactivities. Throughout the entire transient, both models show a negative reactivity insertion due to the fuel and moderator temperature changes, and no recriticality occurs. Notably, the TRACE-SA model presents a more pessimistic scenario. This disparity in total reactivity accounts for the differences observed in total power, as depicted in Figure 5.

Study of SMART ATWS with TRACE-SUBCHANFLOW

Figure 10: Core coolant average temperature.

Figure 11: Total (T), fuel (F) and moderator (M) reactivities.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This study presents an analysis of the ATWS accident for the SMART Reactor, utilizing the TRACE-SA and TRACE-SCF codes. The TRACE-SCF coupling, which incorporates a domain decomposition approach with an explicit time-advancing scheme, was applied successfully to analyze the aforementioned transient.

A comparison of various parameters between the two simulation results was conducted for both steady-state and transient calculations. It was found that the general behavior of all the compared parameters had the same trend, with the exception of the total power predicted by the models, which exhibited a difference attributed to the variance in total reactivity obtained in the simulations.

Throughout the transient, the reactivity inserted into the core due to the TH feedback remained negative, with no SCRAM intervention. The study found no evidence of recriticality during the transient, with the TRACE-SA identified as the pessimistic case from a return-to-criticality perspective.

As part of the upcoming activities within the McSAFER Project, this transient will be further analyzed using the coupled version of TRACE and OpenFOAM, and the results will be compared to identify the most suitable computational methods.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was done within the framework of the McSAFER Project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement No 945063.

REFERENCES

1. Sanchez-Espinoza VH, Gabriel S, Suikkanen H, Telkkä J, Valtavirta V, Bencik M, Kliem S, Queral C, Farda A, Abéguilé F, Smith P, Uffelen PV, Ammirabile L, Seidl M, Schneidesch C, Grishchenko D, Lestani H. "The H2020 McSAFER Project: Main Goals, Technical Work Program, and Status," *Energies*. (2021); 14(19):6348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14196348>

2. IAEA. “Advances in small modular reactor technology developments,” *Supplement to IAEA advanced Reactors Information System (ARIS)*, pages 35-38 (2018).
3. KAERI. “Status report 77 - System-Integrated Modular Advanced Reactor (SMART),” (2011).
4. Y.J. Chung, H.R. Kim, J.H. Chun, S.H. Kim and K.H. Bae. “Strength assessment of SMART design against anticipated transient without scram,” *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 85, pages 617-623 (2015).
5. S. Kliem, M. Garcia, C. Queral, M. Bencik and V. Sanchez-Espinoza. “McSAFER - Milestone MS07: Selection of accident scenarios for WP4”.
6. Bae, K. H., Kim, S. D., Lee, Y. J., Lee, G. H., An, S. J., Lim, S. W., & Kim, Y. I. “Enhanced safety characteristics of SMART100 adopting passive safety systems,” *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 379 (2021).
7. EU Horizon 2020, grant agreement 945063. “McSAFER - High-Performance Advanced Methods and Experimental Investigations for the Safety Evaluation of Generic Small Modular Reactors”. *url: <http://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/945063>*.
8. Young-Jong Chung, Hyung-Rae Kim, Ji-Han Chun, Soo-Hyung Kim, Kyoo-Hwan Bae. “Strength assessment of SMART design against anticipated transient without scram,” *KAERI*, (2015).
9. Y. Alzaben, V. H. Sanchez-Espinoza, and R. Stieglitz, “Core neutronics and safety characteristics of a boron-free core for Small Modular Reactors,” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 132, pp. 70–81, Oct. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.04.017>
10. Y. Alzaben, V.H. Sanchez-Espinoza and R. Stieglitz, “Analysis of a steam line break accident of a generic SMART plant with a boron-free core using the coupled code TRACE/PARCS,” *Nuclear Engineering and design* 350 (2019) 33-42.
11. U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. “TRACE V5.0 USER’S MANUAL”. <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1200/ML120060239.pdf>
12. U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. “TRACE V5.0 PATCH 5 THEORY MANUAL”.
13. Imke U and Sanchez-Espinoza VH. “Validation of the Subchannel Code SUBCHANFLOW Using the NUPEC PWR Tests (PSBT),” *Hindawi Publishing Corporation Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations Volume 2012, Article ID 465059, 12 pages* [doi:10.1155/2012/465059](https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/465059) (2012).